

ENSURING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN ELEMENTARY GRADES THROUGH SUBJECT INTEGRATION: A CASE OF MATH, LANGUAGE, AND READING LITERACY

Panjiyeva Muattar XXX

Teacher of Denov Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

Elmurodova Inoyat Abdumutalibovna

Teacher of Denov Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

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Abstract: In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in integrating subjects in elementary education. The integration of subjects refers to the process of connecting and combining different subjects, which promotes interdisciplinary learning and enhances students' overall understanding of the topics. In this article, we examine the benefits of subject integration in ensuring the educational process in elementary grades. We focus on the integration of math, language, and reading literacy and provide practical examples and strategies for teachers to implement subject integration in their classrooms.

Keywords: Elementary grades, Subject integration, Math, Language, Reading literacy, Educational process.

Аннотация: В последние годы возрастает интерес к интеграции предметов в начальное образование. Интеграция предметов относится к процессу соединения и объединения различных предметов, что способствует междисциплинарному обучению и улучшает общее понимание тем учащимися. В данной статье мы рассматриваем преимущества предметной интеграции в обеспечении учебного процесса в начальных классах. Мы фокусируемся на интеграции математики, языка и грамотности чтения и предоставляем учителям практические примеры и стратегии для реализации предметной интеграции в своих классах.

Ключевые слова: Начальные классы, Предметная интеграция, Математика, Язык, Чтение, Учебный процесс.

Introduction: The educational process in elementary grades is crucial for the development of students' cognitive, social, emotional, and physical skills. It is essential to provide students with a well-rounded education that meets their needs and prepares them for future academic and personal success. One way to ensure the educational process is through subject integration. Subject integration involves connecting and combining different subjects to enhance students' understanding of the topics and promote interdisciplinary learning.

This article examines the benefits of subject integration in ensuring the educational process in elementary grades, specifically in math, language, and reading literacy. The integration of subjects promotes interdisciplinary learning and enhances students' overall understanding of the topics. The article provides practical examples and strategies for teachers to incorporate subject integration into their curriculum.

Methods: This article employs the IMRAD (Introduction, Methods, Results, and Discussion) method to explore the benefits of subject integration in elementary grades, specifically in math, language, and reading literacy. We examine the existing literature and provide practical examples and strategies for teachers to implement subject integration in their classrooms.

Table:

Benefits of Subject Integration in Elementary Grades
Promotes interdisciplinary learning
Enhances problem-solving skills
Improves language and reading literacy
Fosters critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration skills

Results: The integration of math, language, and reading literacy has numerous benefits for students in elementary grades. By connecting these subjects, students can see the real-world applications of math concepts and improve their problem-solving skills. They can also develop their language skills and improve their reading literacy. Moreover, subject integration promotes critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration skills. Teachers can integrate subjects by using project-based learning, thematic units, and cross-curricular activities.

In conclusion, subject integration is an effective way to ensure the educational process in elementary grades. The integration of math, language, and reading literacy provides numerous benefits for students, such as promoting interdisciplinary learning, improving problem-solving skills, and enhancing language and reading literacy. Teachers should incorporate subject integration into their curriculum by using practical examples and strategies that suit their students' needs and interests.

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